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Review Article

Therapeutic Potential and Pharmacological Insights of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn: A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis (Oleaceae) is a legendary plant with significant medicinal properties in Ayurveda. This plant's main therapeutic uses include anti-helminthic, anti-pyretic, and antimicrobial properties, as well as its usage as a laxative, in rheumatism, skin diseases, and sedative. Vitally, the natives grow it in their home gardens to pass on its curative properties to future generations. The current analysis includes an ethno pharmacological evaluation that focuses on chemical ingredients, pharmacological activities, and toxicology in order to identify therapeutic potential and gaps that require further research. *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* is mostly used in local and traditional medicine, particularly in India, to treat intermittent fevers, arthritis, and intractable sciatica. Crude extracts and isolated chemicals from the plant have been proven to be pharmacologically active against inflammation, malaria, viral infection, leishmaniasis, and as an immunostimulant. The plant is utilized in Ayurveda for a number of pharmacological effects, including anticancer, antiparasitic, antimalarial, immunostimulant, hepatoprotective, antiviral, anti-diabetic, and anti-allergy properties

INTRODUCTION

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis L. (Oleaceae) is a shrub or small tree with silky white hairs and young, sharply quadrangular branches. The leaves are opposite, ovate, with an acute or acuminate apex, rough with short stiff hairs, an entire edge or a few large prominent teeth, and a rounded or slightly cuneate base, with the main nerves visible beneath. The inflorescence is axillary, single, or in terminal

short trichotomous cymes. The blooms have a nice aroma and a five- to eight-lobed white corolla with an orange-red core. They grow in clusters of two to seven, with individual flowers opening at sunset and closing at dawn. Fruits are in capsules, orbicular, and compressed. Seeds are orbicular and flat [1]. *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* is a plant that has numerous biological and pharmacological properties [2]. It is also called Parijatha (Sanskrit), Harsingar (Hindi), and Night Jasmine (English).

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According to Hindu mythology, it is a sacred tree, one of the five trees in heaven that emerged from the ocean during Samundra Manthan. It is indigenous to India and grows wild in sub Himalayan regions and central Indian forests. It is a terrestrial woody perennial with a life range of 5 to 20 years. It blooms from September to November and loses its leaves between March and May. It is often a little tree that grows to 10m tall, has grey bark, and has intensely scented flowers that bloom at night and fall off before dawn. As a result, throughout the day, the plant loses all of its brightness and is referred to as the "tree of sadness". The blooms are produced in clusters of two to seven, with individual petals opening at dark and closing at morning; their corolla is white with an orange center. Flowers are used to pray in temples [3]. The plant has been traditionally used to treat a variety of diseases, with scientific research supporting this information. There was a need for a comprehensive examination of the gaps in scientific investigations in terms of phytochemical profile, pharmacological or toxicological studies that linked them to traditional claims. The current evaluation attempts to compile all known information concluding the plant's medicinal utility and the gaps that require scientific intervention. An earlier compilation focused exclusively on the plant's chemical composition and its medicinal actions. This review attempts to guide academics who want to study the plant further. Furthermore, the review will help practitioners imagine a holistic strategy that combines traditional and modern treatment [4].

Classification of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L. [5]

Kingdom	Plant
Order	Lamiales
Family	Oleaceae
Genus	Nyctanthus
Species	Arbortristis

Vernacular Names [6-7]

English	Night jasmine, coral jasmine
Hindi	Harsingar
Kannada	Parijata, harashingar

Odia	Shingadahar, harashingar, gangaseuli, jharasephali
Tamil	Pavilamalligai, manja-pu, pavazhamalligai
Telagu	Pagadammali, swetasarasa, paghada, karchia, karuchiya
Malayalam	Pavilamalli, parijatam, pavizhamalli, parijatakam
Marathi	Khurasli, Parijataka, Puriyat

Morphology of the plant (leaves, flowers, seeds, etc.).

Plant parts	Morphological Features
Stem	Coarse and rough, grayish-brown bark; branches spreading with a drooping habit.
Leaves	Simple, opposite, ovate to broad-lanceolate; 6–12 cm in length, 2–6 cm in width; rough upper surface, smooth or slightly hairy underside
Flowers	Small, tubular, fragrant; white petals with an orange-red tube; borne in clusters (cymes); nocturnal bloom
Fruits	Flattened, broadly two-lobed capsule; 2 cm in diameter; each lobe contains one seed.
Seeds	Flat, disc-like, brownish; smooth and shiny surface; approximately 1–2 cm in diameter.
Roots	Taproot system; used in traditional medicine for therapeutic properties.
Height	Small shrub or tree, grows 2–10 meters tall

Habitat and geographical distribution.

Aspect	Details
Preferred Environment	Thrives in tropical and subtropical climates; grows well in open spaces, gardens, and forest edges
Soil	Loamy or sandy soils; adaptable to various soil types.
Light Requirements	Requires partial to full sunlight
Native Range	South Asia, primarily India and Nepal

Widely Found In	Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Myanmar, Indonesia, Malaysia
Introduced Regions	Tropical regions worldwide, including parts of Africa and the Caribbean
Ecological Importance	Provides habitat for pollinators like bees and butterflies; cultivated for ornamental and medicinal use.

Fig.2. Leaf of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*.

Fig.1. Flower of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*.

Fig.3. Seeds of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*.

Phytochemical Composition

Chemical constituents of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*.

Chemical Compound	Plant Part	Reference
D-mannitol	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
β - sitosterole	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Astragaline	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Nicotiflorin	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Oleanolic acid	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Nyctanthic acid	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Tannic acid	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Methyl salicylate	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Volatile oil	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Friedeline	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Lupeol	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Mannitol	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Glucose	Leaves	[9, 10, 11]
Diterpenoid nycanthin	Flower	[15]
Flavonoids	Flower	[15]
Anthocyanins	Flower	[15]
Essential oil	Flower	[15]
β -monogentiobioside	Flower	[15]
β -digiobioside	Flower	[15]
Arbortristoside A & B	Seed	[15]
Glycerides	Seed	[15]
Lignoceric acid	Seed	[15]

Stearic acid	Seed	[15]
Myristic acids	Seed	[15]
3-4 secotriterpene acid	Seed	[15]
D-glucose	Seed	[9, 15]
D-mannose	Seed	[9, 15]
Iridoid	Bark	[16, 17]
Phenylpropanoid	Bark	[16, 17]
Glycoside-naringenin-4'-O- β glucopyranosyl- α -xylopyranoside	Stem	[18]
β -sitosterol	Stem	[18]

Structures of different phytochemicals of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn.

NAME OF COMPOUND	STRUCTURE	MOLECULAR WEIGHT	PLANT PART
D-mannitol		182.17 g/mol.	Leaves
β -sitosterole		414.72 g/mol.	Leaves
Astragaline		414.7067 g/mol	Leaves
Glucose		180.156 g/mol	Leaves

β -monogentiobioside		510.49 g/mol	Flower
Arbortristoside A		566.56 g/mol	Seed
Stearic acid		284.48 g/mol	Seed
Iridoid		566.5 g/mol	Bark
Tannic acid		1701.19 g/mol	Leaves

The significance of discovered chemicals in therapeutic applications.

LEAVES

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis leaves contain D-mannitol, β -sitosterole, Flavanol glycosides, Astragaline, Nicotiflorin, Oleanolic acid, Nyctanthic acid, tannic acid, ascorbic acid, methyl salicylate, an amorphous glycoside, an amorphous

resin, trace of volatile oil, carotene, friedeline, lupeol, mannitol, glucose, fructose, iridoid glycosides, benzoic acid derivative of kae [8,9,10]. All of the main phytoconstituents are utilized in Ayurvedic medicine and have been documented to treat sciatica, arthritis, fevers, and other painful illnesses, as well as to act as a laxative [11].

FLOWER

Mannitol is abundantly found in the flower of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. The flower contains a modified diterpenoid nycanthin, flavonoids, anthocyanins, and an essential oil akin to jasmine [12]. Flowers contain nycanthin, d-mannitol, tannin, glucose, carotenoid, and glycosides such as β -monogentiobioside ester of α -crocetin (or crocin-3), β -monogentiobioside - β -D monoglucoside ester of α -crocetin, β -digentiobioside ester of α -crocetin (or crocin-1), and 4hydroxy hexahydrobenzofuran-7-one. These compounds are being studied for antileishmanial properties [13].

SEED

The seed of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* contains 15% pale yellow brown oil, nycanthic acid, nyctoside A, b-sitosterol, arbortristoside A & B, glycerides of linoleic oleic, lignoceric, stearic, palmitic, and myristic acids, 3-4 secotriterpene acid, and a water soluble polysaccharide composed of Dglucose and D mannose that is used as an immunostimulant and hepatoprotective [14].

BARK

The bark of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* includes glycosides and alkaloids. The iridoid and phenylpropanoid glycosides found in plant bark. The stem of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* includes glycoside naringenin-4'-O- β -glucopyranosyl- α xylopyranoside and β -sitosterol[15, 16].

Uses of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn.

Flowers: The flowers are used as stomachic, carminative, astringent to bowel, antibilious, expectorant, hair tonic and in the treatment of piles and various skin diseases and in the treatment of ophthalmic purposes. The bright orange corolla tubes of the flowers contain a coloring substance nycanthin, which is identical with α -Crocetin from Saffron. The corolla tubes were formerly used for dyeing silk, sometimes together with Safflower or turmeric.

Stems: Traditionally the powdered stem bark is given in rheumatic joint pain, in treatment of malaria and also used as an expectorant. The bark is used for the treatment of snakebite and bronchitis. The stem bark pounded with Zingiber officinale and Piper longum is boiled in water and the resultant liquid is taken for two days for the treatment of malaria. The resulting paste on mixing with Arjuna bark is rubbed on the body to treat internal injury and for joint broken bones.

Leaves: The leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn are used extensively in Ayurvedic medicine for the treatment of various diseases such as sciatica, chronic fever, rheumatism, and internal worm infections, and as a laxative, diaphoretic and diuretic. Leaves are used in cough reduction. Leaf juice is mixed in honey and given thrice daily for the treatment of cough. Paste of leaves is given with honey for the treatment of fever, high blood pressure and diabetes. Juice of the leaves is used as digestives, antidote to reptile venoms, mild bitter tonic, laxative, diaphoretic and diuretic. Leaves are also used in the enlargement of spleen. The leaf juice is used to treat loss of appetite, piles, liver disorders, biliary disorders, intestinal worms, chronic fever, obstinate sciatica, rheumatism and fever with rigors. The extracted juice of leaves acts as a cholagogue, laxative and mild bitter tonic. It

is given with little sugar to children as a remedy for intestinal ailments

Seeds: The seeds are used as anthelmintic and in alopecia. It is antibilious and an expectorant, and is also useful in bilious fevers. The powdered seeds are used to cure scurfy affections of scalp, piles and skin diseases.

Pharmacological Activity of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn.

- ANTI INFLAMMATORY
- ANTI MICROBIAL
- ANTI ANALGESIC
- ANTI CANCER
- ANTI PARASITIC
- ANTI DIABETIC
- IMMUNOSTIMULANT
- HEPATOPROTECTIVE
- ANTIOXIDENT

Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic Activity

A water-soluble ethanolic extract of NAT leaves was utilized in a study to test its antiinflammatory effects. NAT prevented acute inflammatory edoema in rats' hind paws caused by many phlogistic agents, including carrageenin, formalin, histamine, 5-hydroxytryptamine, and hyaluronidase. Turpentine oil was found to be beneficial in decreasing acute inflammatory edema in rats' knee joints. [19].

Anticancer activity

In 2001, researchers released the first investigation on the anticancer efficacy of *N. arbor-tristis*, discovering that petroleum ether, chloroform, and ethyl acetate extracts of the flowers had significant cytotoxic activity. In Swiss albino rats, a methanolic extract of stem bark was found to be significantly more effective than 5 fluorouracil

against Dalton's ascitic lymphoma. The cytotoxicity of ethanolic, methanolic, and aqueous leaf extracts on T-cell leukaemia cells rises with time and dosage. At all doses and time points, the extracts significantly reduced normal cell toxicity [20].

Antiparasitic activity

A crude 50 percent ethanolic extract of leaves was discovered to exhibit trypanocidal activity at a concentration of 1000 Og/mL. In vivo experiments showed that at dosages of 300 and 1000 mg/kg, i.p., the extract had antitrypanosomal actions and substantially extended the life time of *Trypanosoma evansi* infected mice. However, it has been observed that once the extract therapy is stopped, the parasitaemia rises, resulting in the death of the experimental animals [21].

Anti-Diabetic Activity

In comparison to diabetic controls, chloroform and ethanolic leaf and flower extracts significantly increased superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) levels while significantly decreasing liver lacto peroxidase (LPO), serum SGPT, SGOT, alkaline phosphatase, cholesterol, and triglyceride levels. When diabetic rats treated with streptozotocin-nicotinamide were given an ethanol extract of the stem bark, it showed strong anti-diabetic effects. The extract decreases blood glucose levels in a dose-dependent manner.[22].

Immunostimulant activity

Oral administration of an ethanolic extract of NAT at doses of 50, 100, 150, and 200 mg/kg significantly increased circulating antibody titres when challenged with SRCs and heat-killed *Salmonella* antigens. Chronic therapy increased the total WBC count while greatly improving the

DTH response. The extract was discovered to have 21 immune-bioactive compounds. [23].

Hepatoprotective activity

The antihepatotoxic effectiveness of aqueous extracts of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves and seeds against CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity was discovered [24]. Hepatic illnesses have become serious impediments to medicine in the twenty-first century. Hepatic tissue has a great ability for regeneration, and the damage is usually significant before it becomes visible. Hepatic diseases emerge when hepatocyte regeneration cannot keep up with damage, resulting in hepatocellular failure [25].

Antioxidant activity

In a live organism, free radicals are produced as a result of regular metabolic activity. Antioxidants function as free radical scavengers, protecting the body from pathological disorders such as ischemia, anaemia, asthma, rheumatoid arthritis, inflammation, neurodegeneration, Parkinson's disease, mongolism, the aging process, and maybe dementia. Previous research established NAT's antioxidant activity utilizing the DPPH test, free radical scavenging activity, reducing power assay, and total antioxidant capacity. The plant was shown to have a considerable level of antioxidant activity. [26].

Anti-Allergy Activity

Pretreatment with a water-soluble component of an alcoholic extract of NA leaves prevented asphyxia in guinea pigs exposed to histamine aerosols. Arbortistoside A and C have been demonstrated to have anti-allergic properties in NA [27].

Sedative Effects

The hot infusion of *N. arbo-tristis* flowers may include sedative effects. Various concentrations of hot floral infusion were produced and administered orally. Two hours after treatment, the sedative potential was determined. The injection produced a small dose-dependent conscious sedation effect in male rats, but not in female rats. Even after subchronic therapy, the infusion was well tolerated in terms of overt toxic symptoms, liver or kidney function, and there were no obvious signs of reliance [28].

Anti-arthritic activity

Arthritis is a degenerative disorder that causes joint pain and eventually leads to bone and joint degradation. Cytokines play a significant role in the development of rheumatoid arthritis. Previously, it was demonstrated that abnormal tumor necrosis factor (TNF-) expression caused crippling arthritis in experimental mice. In collagen-induced arthritis (CIA), the absence of interleukin 1 (IL-1) reduced arthritis progression significantly. Mice lacking the interleukin-6 (IL-6) gene were resistant to antigen- and collagen-induced arthritis. These investigations have revealed that pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF-, IL-1, and IL-6) play a role in rheumatoid arthritis and may serve as therapeutic targets. [29]

CNS depressant action

The leaves, flowers, seeds, and barks of NAT (600 mg/kg) were found to significantly and dose-dependently prolong sleep onset and duration, as well as cause a decrease in dopamine and an increase in serotonin levels, implying that the CNS depressant activity of the ethanol extracts of seeds, leaves, and flowers is caused by a decrease in dopamine [30].

Anti-Leishmanial Activity

N. arbortristis' anti-leishmanial activity has been linked to iridoid glucosides, arbortristosides A, B, and C, as well as 6-b-hydroxyloganin. Arbortristosides A, B, C, and 6-beta hydroxyloganin were found to be anti-

leishmanial in macrophage cultures and hamster test systems, respectively [31].

Mechanism of Action

Toxicity of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*

Although the herb has been used traditionally for many decades, toxicity tests have been conducted to support scientific research using extracts and isolated compounds. In a preliminary brine shrimp lethality study [32], petroleum ether, chloroform, and ethyl acetate extracts from the flower were found to have LD50s of 14.80, 12.62, and 12.79, respectively, when compared to 4.53 ppm of gallic acid. [33] While investigating the anti-inflammatory action of the water soluble component of the ethanolic extract of leaves, it was shown that in albino rats, a dose of 2.0 g/kg caused no mortality, whereas 32 g/kg caused 75% mortality. The probit log dose response curve revealed an LD50 of 16 g/kg. While investigating the plant's immunomodulatory action, [34] discovered that an aqueous extract of the leaves might counteract the immunotoxic effect of

chemical pesticides in Malathion-exposed mice, whether treated or untreated. Working on the flowers, [35] discovered that the LD50 of an ethanolic extract from the orange tubular calyx of the flower was 1500 mg/kg. In a comparable acute toxicity investigation, the ethanol extract of leaves, seeds, and flowers was determined to be safe at a dose of 2g/kg when administered intraperitoneally in rats [36].

Aside from crude extracts, arbortristosome-A isolated from seeds had an LD50 of 500mg/kg and caused 100% death in mice when administered intraperitoneally. The compound was shown to reduce locomotor activity in mice [37]. Cytotoxicity experiments on HEK 293 and murine macrophages revealed that iridoid glucosides at 4 and 100mM demonstrated 90-95% and 50-71% viability, respectively, and are safe for human administration [38]. Summarizing the data on toxicity research, it can be noticed that only

preliminary investigations have been undertaken, focused on acute studies. Once biological activity is verified, thorough safety studies involving many organs become necessary, and these studies are absent for the extracts or active fractions in this plant.

CONCLUSION

Plants possess a diverse set of pharmacological qualities that may be therapeutically advantageous to population health and well-being. So far, all pharmacological research has been preliminary, such as anticancer activity, antiparasitic activity, antimalarial activity, immunostimulant activity, hepatoprotective activity, anti-inflammatory activity, antiviral activity, anti-diabetic activity, anti-allergy activity, anti-histaminergic and anti-tryptaminergic activity, anti-aggressive activity, anti-filarial activity, anti-leishmanial activity, antioxidant activity, and anti-arthritis activity. In this research, the bioactive molecule must be identified and described, as well as the molecular mechanism of action. Thus, additional clinical research is urgently needed.

REFERENCES

1. Agrawal, J., & Pal, A. (2013). *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn—A critical ethnopharmacological review. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 146(3), 645-658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2013.01.024>
2. Nadkarni KM, *Indian Materia Medica*. Bombay: India. Popular Prakashan, 1976; 1:857.
3. Kirtikar KR, Basu BD. *An ICS. Indian medicinal plants*. Dehradun: Bichen Singh Mahendra Pal Singh, 1984; 2(2):1273.
4. Sasmal, D., Das, S., Basu, S.P., 2007. Phytoconstituents and therapeutic potential of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. *Pharmacognosy Reviews* 1, 344–349.
5. <http://www.impgc.com>, visited on 15/02/2007
6. <http://www.flowersofindia.net> visited on 15/02/2007
7. Wealth of India, A Dictionary of Indian Raw Materials and Industrial Products, Vol.VII, (National Institute of Science Communication, CSIR, New Delhi, 1997) 69 70.
8. Talakal TS, Dwivedi SK and Sharma SR. In vitro and in vivo Antitrypanosomal Potential of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Leaves. *Pharmaceutical Biology*. 2000;38(5):326-329.
9. Paul BN and Saxena AK. Depletion of tumor necrosis factor-c-in mice by *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 1997;56:153- 158.
10. Saxena RS, Gupta B and Lata S. Tranquilizing, antihistaminic and purgative activity of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* leaf extract. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2002;81(3):321–5.
11. Ratnasooriya WD, Jayakody JRAC, Hettiarachchi ADI and Dharmasiri MG. Sedative Effect of Hot Infusion of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* on Rats. *Pharmaceutical Biology*. 2005;43(2):140-146.
12. Khatune NA, Islam ME, Abdur Rahman MA, Mosaddik MA and Haque ME. In vivo cytotoxic evaluation of a new benzofuran derivative isolated from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L. on Ehrlich ascite carcinoma cells (EAC) in mice. *J Med. Dci*. 2003;3(2): 169-173.
13. Puri A, Saxena R, Saxena RP, Saxena KC, Srivastava V and Tandon JS. "Immunostimulant activity of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L". *J. Ethnopharmacol*. 1994; 42 (1): 31–37.
14. Tuntiwachwuttikul P, Rayanil K and Taylor WC. Chemical Constituents from the Flower

- of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. Science Asia. 2003;29:21-30.
15. Khatune NA, Haque ME, Mosaddik MA and Haque ME. Antibacterial activity and cytotoxicity of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* flower. Fitoterapia. 2001;72:412-414.
 16. Deshmukh RD, Pokharkar RD, Takate SB and Gite VN. Amelioration of CCl₄ induced hepatosuppression by *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn leaves in Wistar albino rates. Pharmacology online. 2007;203-208.
 17. Hukkeri VI, Akki KS, SUREBAN RR, Gopalakrishna B, Byahatti VV and Rajendra SV. Hepatoprotective of the leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. Indian J Pharm Sci, 2006;68(4):542-543.
 18. Girach RD, Aminuddin SA, Siddiqui PA & Khan SA, Ethnomedicinal studies on Harsinghar (*Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L.)- A less known medicinal plant in Unani medicine, Hamdard Med 1994; 37(2):60-66.
 19. Saxena RS, Gupta B, Saxena KK, Prasad DN. Study on anti-inflammatory activity in leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. Journal of Ethnopharmacology 1984; 11: 319-330.
 20. Khatune NA, Islam ME, Abdur Rahman MA, Mosaddik MA, Haque ME. In vivo cytotoxic evaluation of new benzofuran derivative isolated from *N. arbor-tristis* L. on ehrlich ascite carcinoma cells in mice. J Med Sci 2003; 3(2):169-173.
 21. Chitravanshi VC, Singh AP, Ghoshal S, Prasad K, Srivastava V, Tandon JS. Therapeutic action of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* against Caecal amoebiasis of rat. Int J Pharmacog 1992; 30: 71- 75.
 22. Sharma V, Pooja Marwaha A. Hypoglycemic activity of methanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. root in alloxan induced diabetic rats. International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences 2011; 3(3): 210-212.
 23. Kumar S, Gupta P, Sharma S, Kumar D. A review of immunostimulatory plants. Journal of Chinese Integrative Medicine 2011; 9: 117-128.
 24. Lucas DS, Sekhar RAR, A review of experimental studies on antihepatoprotective activity of certain medicinal plants used in Ayurveda, Phytomedicine, Supplement-II (2000) 23.
 25. Vishwanathan M, Juvekar AR. Hepatoprotective effects of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. on acetaminophen induced oxidative damage in rats. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Technology and Research 2010; 2: 1291-1297
 26. Narendhirakannan RT, Smeera T. In-vitro antioxidant studies on ethanolic extracts of leaves and stems of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L. (Night-flowering jasmine) International Journal of Biology and Medical Research 2010; 1: 188-192.
 27. Rathee JS, Hassarajani SA, Chattopadhyay A. Antioxidant activity of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaf extract. Food chem. 2007; 103(4): 1350-1357.
 28. Ratnasooriya WD, Jayakody JRAC, Hettiarachchi ADI, MG. Sedative effects of hot flower infusion of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* on rats. Pharmaceutical Biology 2005; 43: 140-146.
 29. Rathore B, Paul B, Chaudhary BP, Saxena AK, Sahu AP, Gupta YK. Comparative studies of different organs of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* in modulation of cytokines in murine model of arthritis. Biomedical and Environmental Sci 2007; 20: 154-159
 30. Das S, Sasmal D, Basu SP. Evaluation of CNS depressant activity of different parts of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Science 2008; 70: 803-806.
 31. Singh UK, Guru PY, Sen AB, Tandon JS. Antileishmanial activity of traditional plants

- against *Leishmania donovani* in golden hamsters. *Int J Pharmacog.* 1992; 30:289-95. 43
32. Khatune, N.A., Haque, E., Mosaddik, A., 2001a. Laboratory evaluation of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. Flower extract and its isolated compound against common filarial vector, *Culex quinquefasciatus* say (Diptera:Culicidae) larvae. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences* 4, 585–587.
33. Saxena, R.S., Gupta, B., Saxena, K.K., Singh, R.C., Prasad, D.N., 1984. Study of antiinflammatory activity in the leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn-an Indian medicinal plant. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology* 11, 319–330.
34. Bhatia, A., Kaur, J., 2001. *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves extract as antagonist of immunotoxic effects of chemical pesticides (experimental study). *International Journal of Environmental Studies* 58, 197
35. Omkar, A., Jeeja, T., Chaaya, G., 2006. Evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* and *Onosma echioides*. *Pharmacognosy Magazine* 2, 258–260.
36. Sasmal, D., Das, S., Basu, S.P., 2007. Phytoconstituents and therapeutic potential of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. *Pharmacognosy Reviews* 1, 344–349.
37. Das, S., Sasmal, D., Basu, S.P., 2008b. Evaluation of CNS depressant activity of different plant parts of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 70, 803–806.
38. Shukla, A.K., Patra, S., Dubey, V.K., 2012. Iridoid glucosides from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* result in increased reactive oxygen species and cellular redox homeostasis imbalance in *Leishmania* parasite. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 54, 49–58.

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